

COMPUTER SIMULATION AND WALL CHART ON SENIOR SECONDARY PHYSICS STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT ON WAVES IN EKET LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of computer simulation and wall charts on senior secondary physics students' achievement on waves in Eket Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The study was guided by three research questions and hypotheses. The quasi-experimental design involved an estimated population of 1330 SS2 physics students from eight coeducational public secondary schools. A sample of 150 students was drawn from two schools using simple random sampling. Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Problem-Solving Ability Test (PSAT) were used for data collection, with reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.86, respectively. Two lesson plans were developed for treatment. Pre-test and post-test were administered to intact groups. Mean statistics answered research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) tested hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a significant difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught using computer simulation and those taught using wall charts. The study concludes that computer simulation improves academic performance and promotes long-lasting learning, especially for abstract topics like waves. It recommends incorporating computer simulation into physics teaching strategies, especially for topics like waves.

Keywords: Computer simulation, wall chart, problem-solving ability, gender, lecture method and waves.

Introduction

Education is the life wire of every nation, it has been conceptualized by different scholars as the act of giving or receiving systematic instructions, acquiring knowledge as well as developing reasoning capacities which enables individuals to become functional members of the society (Chukwurah, 2022). According to Diquito, Dhaniaputri and Acuna (2025), education is a tool that avails people with knowledge, skills, technique and information which empowers them to know their rights and duties toward the family, society and the nation. It is conscious and deliberate effort to create an atmosphere of learning and the learning processes that learners are actively developing the potential for them to have self-control personality, intelligence, noble character and the skills needed by them and the society. The authors maintained that education helped in no small

measure to improve the quality of life in any society.

According to Udoh, Udo and Aniedu (2019), science education plays a vital role in the lives of individuals and the development of a nation. It is generally acknowledged that the survival of a nation scientifically and technologically can only be achieved through science education which offers opportunities for science teachers to transmit meaningful learning through innovative teaching strategies which could reverse poor academic achievement and enhance retention of students in the subject.

Science is defined as a body of knowledge, a way or method of investigating and a way of thinking in the pursuit of understanding nature. The aim of teaching and studying

science is to encourage and enable students to achieve the broader objectives of science, which include acquiring process skills, knowledge, and curiosity, as well as developing skills of scientific inquiry to design and conduct scientific investigations and draw evidence-based conclusions. As a branch of science, physics has a significant impact on nations, enabling them to advance technologically (Abidoeye, 2021).

According to Effiong and Onwioduokit (2019), Physics is a branch of science that deals with the fundamental constituents of the universe, the forces they exert on one another and the effects of these forces. Physics as one of the science subjects involves both theoretical and practical experiences. Among the sciences, physics is considered a fundamental subject. Academic achievement in physics is influenced by motivation and teaching methods. Research has shown that both teachers and students' attitude toward physics is a major reason for low academic performance in the subject across the globe (Naki 2018).

According to Podgursky, Monroe and Watson (2012), academic achievement of students in physics has been below expectation and unimpressive. The persistent failure in physics had remained a major threat to its learning. Poor performance of students in physics can be attributed to many factors such as perceived abstract and difficult nature of physics, poor mathematical ability of students, and inadequate modern laboratory equipment for practical work, insufficient physics books and poor instructional delivery approaches. To minimize the failure rate in physics, Aina (2023) pointed out that physics teachers have to be trained and re-trained, adequate modern laboratory facilities should be provided and better teaching strategies should be adopted.

According to Bello and Smetana (2011), computer simulations are computer generated dynamic models that present theoretical or simplified models of real-world components, phenomena or process. They can include animations, visualizations, text, images, video clips and interactive laboratory experiences. Computer simulation is an imitation of a real concept or process. Computer simulation is the use of a computer to represent the dynamic responses of one system by the behavior of another system modeled after it. Hursen and Asiksoy (2015) in their study found that simulation speeds up teachers' educational potential and students' learning thereby allowing students to learn by discovery methods.

The wall chart is a type of large poster often displaying information for educational use or entertainment. Wall chart can be used to introduce a new concept, a process, a course, a programme, a product or a service. The wall chart is an effective tool for teaching physics. This is because students can understand the lesson better through the visual image on the wall chart. Wall chart are not designed for decoration only but primarily to assist with the study of one topic or the other. (Azizah, 2016).

Problem-solving ability is a primary factor to academic achievement in science. Most of what is taught in science requires ability to think. Cognitive abilities are brain-based skills and mental processes that are needed to carry out any task from the simplest to the most complex. Many crises in science education have been partly traced to inability of students to think logically in scientific situations. There are three abilities in relation to teaching and learning situation, viz: High, medium and low (Achor and Ejeh, 2019).

Chumba, Omwenga and Atemi (2020) carried out a study to find out the effect of the use of computer simulations on academic

achievement of form two learners in physics in Ainamoi sub-county in Kericho County. The overall students' performance in physics nationally and in Ainamoi sub-county at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Examination level remained low over the past years. The research objectives were to determine: The effect of using computer simulation on attitude of the experimental groups towards computer simulated physics lessons and the difference between academic achievement of the control group and the experimental group in physics after treatment. The study applied quasi-experimental design involving Solomon (four) non-equivalent control group approach. The study sample consist of 200 form two students and four (4) physics teachers from four (4) mixed day schools sampled purposively. Data was collected using a Standardized Physics Achievement Test (SPAT) and students' questionnaire on Attitude towards Computer Simulated Physics Lesson Scale (ATCSPLS). The experimental groups were taught magnetic effect of electric current using computer simulations. The two control groups on the other hand were taught the same content using conventional methods of instruction. Findings indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between the use of computer simulations and attitude towards physics lessons ($r=0.560$, $p=0.000$). The study revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in academic achievement between the control and experimental groups ($t=-7.531$, $df=193.338$, $p=0.000$). It was recommended that learning should integrate computer simulations in physics subject since they enhance positive attitude in learners and also high academic achievement.

Lasisi, Oti, Arowolo, Agbeyenku, Ojoko (2021) carried out a study to investigate the effect of innovative computer simulated instruction on students' academic

performance in abstract concepts in science. The study adopted quasi-experimental research with pre-test and post-test before and after the treatment respectively. A total of 155 students participated in the study. The experimental group were taught using conventional lecture method. An instrument named Science Concepts Achievement Test (SCAT) were employed to generate data. The obtained data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses respectively.

The study reveals that, computer simulation enhanced students' learning of abstract concepts than the use of conventional lecture method. Results, also revealed that gender did not influence students' academic performance in abstract science concepts significantly when taught with computer simulations. The study therefore, recommend based on the findings of this study, that science teachers should integrate innovative simulation into their instructional modes especially, when teaching abstract concepts. There should be in-service training for science teachers on development and how to access appropriate computer simulations for their lessons. The stereotype superiority of male in learning science should be discarded and both sexes should be equally encouraged to learn science.

Onasanya and Omosewo (2011) conducted a study to examine the effect of wall chart and standard instructional materials on secondary school students' academic performance in physics in Ilorin, Nigeria. The sample consisted of selected secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis of Kwara state. The research employed a quasi-experimental design of the pre-test, post-test non-randomized control group design. Two hypotheses were designed and tested at 0.05 level of significance. From the analysis, the following findings were made: Those taught with wall chart, mean scores on the post-test ($t=4.09$, $df=14$,

$p=0.05$). There was no significant difference between the post-test scores of the experimental group and control group. This shows that wall chart were used to compare the male mean scores of experimental and control groups. Mean scores of both the experimental and control groups were the same entry level with regards to academic ability ($t<1.23$, $df=7$, $p=0.05$). The implications of wall chart were discussed. Recommendations for the improvement of standard instructional aids in the teaching of physics.

Gunawan, Suranti, Nisrina and Herayanti (2018) carried out a study on students' problem-solving skills in physics teaching with virtual labs. Problem solving is a high-level ability to find solution to a problem. In the problem-solving process, students have to identify and understand the problems, plan and review the resolution process. This ability is needed by students to produce meaningful knowledge. This study discusses the effect of virtual lab in physics learning toward student's problem-solving abilities. The improvement of problem-solving skills was analyzed in each step of the solution process.

This quasi-experimental study was conducted at three different senior high schools. There were 165 students in this study, all of whom were divided into three experimental groups and three control groups. The results showed that the problem-solving ability of the experimental group was higher than that of the control group at each school. The analysis of each problem-solving step showed that, in each school, the student's ability to identify and defined the problem and also to establish goals and objectives shows a similar result. Some students have an excellent ability in identifying problem and also have to plan for problem solving. As for the step of analyzing the choice of ideas and steps to follow up in problem solving most of them still need to be

improved. Students who are viable to complete a particular problem-solving step will not be able to complete the next.

Umoru (2016) defined gender as a socio-cultural and psychological dimension of being a male or female. There might have been conflicting reports with respect to gender and performance in science. The author noted that gender is not a significant factor in students' achievement, since there is improvement in both male and female achievement.

According to Anyakoha (2016), a wave is a disturbance which travels through a medium and transfer energy from one point to another without causing any permanent displacement of the medium itself. It is a pattern generated in a medium when a disturbance (energy) travel from one point to the other point with no transport of particles. There are two classes of waves: Mechanical waves and electromagnet waves.

Lecture method is defined as a technique in which one person, normally the teacher presents a spoken discourse on a particular subject. The lecture method is used for expounding, simplifying, classifying and discussing new materials with learners. The materials may include facts or views on issues and problems related to the learners which provide as aesthetically stimulating experience. The effectiveness of the lecture method depends on the type of the class, the students, the circumstances of the class, the subject, educational purpose and the teachers' own characteristics and skills (Ebokaiwe, Ajaja and kpangban, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal physics classroom, senior secondary students would have access to engaging and interactive learning resources that facilitate their understanding of complex concepts, such as waves and enable them to achieve academic excellence. However, in many secondary schools in Eket Local

Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, physics students often struggle to grasp the concepts of waves due to the lack of adequate and effective teaching resources, resulting in poor academic performance and limited understanding of the subject matter. Continuous high failure rate among physics students calls for serious concern. Exposure to internal and external examinations, whether West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination Council, National Examination Council and Joint Admission and Matriculation Board shows students not achieving well. This poses a threat to knowledge input among students for future performances either at the tertiary level of education or in the world of work. This needs to be tackled and the gap filled.

In doing so, available, effective and efficient teaching resources could be incorporated alongside with other teaching strategies to improve students' academic performance. It is unfortunate to note that most physics teachers do not use teaching resources even when they are available particularly the visual type such as wall chart and the electronic interactive such as computer simulations which are capable of capturing students' interest and stimulate curiosity towards the lesson. Waves is an important and interesting concept in physics. Despite its applications in day-to-day life, students' still find it abstract and difficult. This could be because of the way it is being taught or the students does not have the required learning materials. Teachers have difficulty making the concept real to students' understanding. It is on this basis that the study examines how computer simulation and wall charts will impact on senior secondary physics students' achievement on waves in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of computer simulation and wall chart

on senior secondary physics students' achievement on waves in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the difference in achievement mean scores between physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart;
2. Investigate the difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart;
3. Compare the achievement mean scores of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference in achievement mean scores between physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart?
2. Is there a significant difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart?
3. What is the difference in achievement mean scores among physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in achievement mean scores between physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart;
2. There is no significant difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught

waves using computer simulation and wall chart;

- There is no significant difference among the achievement mean scores of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design that was adopted for the study is non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group design. This quasi experimental design is chosen because it allows for students to be taught in their intact class setting. The design is structurally shown as:

$$\begin{array}{rclclcl} E & = & O_1 & X_1 & O_2 \\ C & = & O_3 & X_2 & O_4 \end{array}$$

Where:

E = Experimental group taught using computer simulation;

C = Control group taught using wall charts;

O₁, O₃ = Pre-test observations in respect to E and C respectively;

O₂, O₄ = Post-test observations in respect to E and C respectively;

X₁ = Treatment with computer simulation;

X₂ = Treatment with wall charts.

The study was carried out in Eket Local Government Area.

The population comprised all the senior secondary two (SSII) physics students in the eight (8) co-educational public secondary schools in Eket Local Government Area for the 2024/2025 academic session. The estimated population size was one thousand, three hundred and thirty (1330) students.

The study sample consisted of 150 Senior Secondary two (SSII) students drawn from two public secondary schools in Eket Local Government Area using simple random sampling technique. An intact physics class of

Senior Secondary School two (SS II) in the two Secondary Schools was selected and assigned randomly into the experimental and control groups. The experimental and the control groups of the first school consist of 45 and 35 students in their intact class settings while the experimental and the control groups of the second school consist of 35 and 35 students in their intact class settings.

Instruments that was used for data collection are: Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Problem-Solving Ability Test (PSAT). The PAT is a researcher made instrument with 40 multiple choice items having four options A, B, C and D. Among the four options, there is one correct option and three distractors. The items were drawn to cover waves concepts such as definition of waves, classes of waves, types of mechanical waves, properties of waves, terms used in wave motion, wave equations and calculations in waves.

The PSAT is a researcher made instrument with 40 multiple choice items having four options A, B, C and D. Among the four options, there is one correct option and three distractors. The items were drawn to cover concepts in physics such as speed, velocity and acceleration, Newton's laws of motion, electric field (Ohm's law, electrical energy and power), projectiles, wave equations, elasticity, work energy and power, heat energy and temperature, mechanical energy, motion (equations of motion, harmonic motion) and vectors. The content in the behavioral objectives were tested based on knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation.

Validation of the instruments

The drafted instruments- Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Problem-Solving Ability Test (PSAT) were deemed valid when the content of the instruments measures what it was intended to measure

accurately. To ensure validity of the instruments, the instruments were given to a team of three experts made of two experienced physics teachers and one specialist in test, measurement and evaluation. To achieve face validity, the validators scrutinized the instruments in terms of proper wording of items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items for the study. For content validity, the test blue print of both PAT and PSAT were given to the validators to examine and ensure that the test content was representative of the area of interest and in line with the lower cognitive educational objectives. In general, the comments and recommendations of the validators helped to modify the PAT and PSAT from the initial 60 items to a final version with 40 items.

Reliability of the instruments

In order to ascertain the reliability of the research instruments - Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Problem-Solving Ability Test (PSAT) were administered to thirty (30) Senior Secondary Two (SSII) Physics students in one of the coeducational secondary school in Eket Local Government Area that was not part of the sample. The data collected from the pilot test was analyzed by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The reliability coefficient index of 0.81 was realized in PAT while the reliability coefficient index of 0.86 was obtained in PSAT.

Research Procedure

The procedure used was as follows: In week 1, the researcher visited the selected schools and obtained permission from the principals of the selected schools to use their schools for the research study. In the same week 1, the consent of the students to be used for the study was sought for and obtained. In week 2, training of one research assistant each from the two schools was done. The two research assistants were trained on computer

simulation method and lecture method on the topic selected for both experimental and control groups. The researcher briefed them on the number of weeks the treatment and the teaching strategies will last. The researcher further trained them by reviewing the two (2) lesson notes prepared by the researcher (this helped them to be familiarized with the content, behavioural objectives and activities of the teacher and students during the instructional process}. The experimental group1 was instructed using computer simulation method while the control group 2 was instructed using lecture method (wall charts). The instruction lasted for 160 minutes for two (2) weeks with each lesson lasting for 40 minutes. At the end of the treatment in week four (4), the same test was administered to the same groups of students and both scores for experimental group1 and control group 2 were recorded accordingly. Three weeks later, precisely in week 8, retention was administered to both the experimental group1 and control group 2 of the two schools. This is done by re-shuffling the PAT and PSAT before administering it back to the students. The scores of the two groups of the two schools were recorded.

Method of Data Analysis

The mean and standard deviation was used to answer research question while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test hypothesis at .05 level of significance.

Ethical Issues

The letter of permission was presented to the principals of the schools sampled for the study. The sample students were duly informed about the research thus getting their consent to take part in the study. The sampled students were expected to participate freely in the study but if need arises, they can exit. Data collected from the study was handled confidentially.

The research procedure or data collected did not cause any harm to the study sample and research assistance. Assurance was given that the data collected shall be treated in strict confidence and used only for academic purposes.

Results

Research Question One

What is the difference in achievement mean scores between physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart?

Table 1: Mean difference in achievement scores of physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Variables	N	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	Mean Diff.	Mean Gain
		Pretest	Posttest		
Computer Simulation	80	49.48	79.26	29.78	
Wall chart	70	39.12	41.90	2.78	27.00

Analysis in Table 1 indicated that the achievement mean score difference of students taught waves using computer simulation was 29.78 greater than the achievement mean score of students exposed to wall chart 2.78. The mean gain between computer simulation and wall chart was 27.00. This implies that the academic achievement mean scores of students taught

waves using computer simulation was better than those taught waves using wall chart.

Research Question Two

Is there a significant difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart?

Table 2: Mean difference in achievement scores between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Group	Gender	N	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	Mean Diff.	Mean Gain
			Pretest	Posttest		
Computer Simulation	Male	33	49.51	77.63	28.12	26.15(Male) 23.80(Female)
	Female	47	46.59	73.08	26.49	
Wall chart	Male	30	40.54	42.51	1.97	
	Female	40	39.12	41.81	2.69	

Analysis in Table 2 indicated the achievement mean score difference between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart. The results show that male students taught waves using computer simulation had a higher mean difference (28.12) compared to those taught waves using wall chart (1.97), resulting in the mean gain of (26.15). Female students taught waves using computer simulation had a higher

mean difference (26.49) compared to those taught waves using wall chart (2.69), resulting in the mean gain of (23.80). This implies that the academic achievement of male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation was better than those taught waves using wall chart.

Research Question Three

What is the difference in achievement mean scores among physics students with high,

medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall charts?

Table 3: Mean difference in achievement scores of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Group	Gender	N	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	Mean Diff.	Mean Gain
			Pretest	Posttest		
Computer Simulation	High	36	50.05	74.83	24.78	
	Medium	28	49.46	62.64	13.18	
	Low	16	48.25	59.18	10.93	
						23.36 (High)
						8.51 (Medium)
Wall chart	High	33	40.54	41.96	1.42	9.5 (Low)
	Medium	30	36.53	41.20	4.67	
	Low	7	43.57	45.00	1.43	

Analysis in Table.3 indicated the achievement mean score difference of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart. The results show that students with high problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation had a higher mean difference (24.78) compared to those taught waves using wall chart (1.42), resulting in the mean gain of (23.36). Students with medium problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation had a higher mean difference (13.18) compared to those taught waves using wall chart (4.67), resulting in the mean gain of (8.51). Students with low problem-solving

abilities taught waves using computer simulation had a higher mean difference (10.93) compared to those taught waves using wall chart (1.43), resulting in the mean gain of (9.50). This implies that the academic achievement of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation was better than those taught waves using wall chart.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in achievement mean scores between physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart;

Table 4: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of physics students’ academic achievement scores when taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Source	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	52290.074 ^a	2	26145.037	540.292	.000	S
Intercept	7035.795	1	7035.795	145.396	.000	
Pretest	174.368	1	174.368	3.603	.060	
Group	26317.308	1	26317.308	543.852	.000	
Error	7113.419	147	48.391			
Total	632784.000	150				

Corrected Total	59403.493	149
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a. R Squared = .880 (Adjusted R-Squared = .879)

The summary of data analysis in Table 4 presented the observed F-value as 540.292. This value was compared with its significant value of .000 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the significant value of .000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the achievement mean scores of physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart is

rejected. This showed that computer simulation is statistically significant as it enhances students’ academic achievement in the teaching of waves.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in achievement mean scores between male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart;

Table 5: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) between male and female physics students’ academic achievement scores when taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	40981.558 ^a	4	10245.389	98.196	.000	S
Intercept	5013.562	1	5013.562	48.052	.000	
Pretest Gender Group	358.499	1	358.499	3.436	.066	
Gender	21107.116	1	21107.116	202.300	.000	
Gender	116.499	1	116.499	1.117	.002	
Group Gender	131.144	1	131.144	1.257	.010	
Error	15128.715	145	104.336			

a. R Squared = .730 (Adjusted R-Squared = .723)

The summary of data analysis in Table 5 presented the observed F-value as 98.196. This value was compared with its significant value of .000 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the significant value of .000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the achievement mean scores of male and female physics students taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using

wall chart is rejected. This showed that computer simulation is statistically significant as it enhances the academic achievement male and female physics students.

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference among the achievement mean scores of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart.

Table 6: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of academic achievement scores of physics student with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities when taught waves using computer simulation and wall chart

Source	Type III Sum Squares	of df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	28071.880 ^a	6	4678.647	36.072	.000	S
Intercept	5959.828	1	5959.828	45.950	.000	
Pretest PSA	22.256	1	22.256	.172	.679	
Group	9062.093	1	9062.093	69.869	.000	
Problem_Solving_Abilities	1433.013	2	716.507	5.524	.005	
Group * PSA	1783.820	2	891.910	6.877	.001	
Error	18547.380	143	129.702			

a. R Squared = .651 (Adjusted R-Squared = .415)

The summary of data analysis in Table 6 presented the observed F-value as 36.072. This value was compared with its significant value of .000 at 0.05 alpha level. Since the significant value of .000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the achievement mean scores of physics students with high, medium and low problem-solving abilities taught waves using computer simulation and those taught using wall chart is rejected. This showed that computer simulation is statistically significant as it enhances students' academic achievement with different problem-solving abilities.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of computer simulation and wall chart on senior secondary physics students' achievement on waves in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. From the findings, it is evident that computer simulation significantly enhanced students' academic achievement more than wall chart. The positive effect of computer simulation was observed not only in the overall students' population but also across gender groups and different levels of problem-solving ability. This suggests that computer simulation is a powerful instructional tool

capable of improving learning outcomes regardless of individual learner differences. In conclusion, the use of computer simulation in teaching Physics, particularly in the topic of waves, can bring about meaningful academic improvement and long-lasting learning among students. It therefore becomes necessary for teachers, curriculum developers, school administrators, and policy makers to recognize the value of digital instructional strategies and make deliberate efforts to incorporate them into classroom practices.

Recommendations

1. Physics teachers should incorporate computer simulations into their regular instructional strategies, especially when teaching abstract topics like waves.
2. The Ministry of Education should organize regular workshops and training sessions for both male and female teachers on gender-sensitive and technology-driven teaching strategies to ensure inclusiveness.
3. Teacher training institutions should incorporate ICT-based instructional methods into their pre-service training programs to equip future teachers with the skills to handle diverse learners effectively.

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